

Title: Which machine learning algorithm(s) can be used for specific problem at hand?

Name: Marzieh Mehrjoo, PhD

Affiliation: Dimensional Strategies Inc., Mississauga, ON, Canada

ABSTRACT:

This presentation discusses what factors should be considered and the questions that need to be answered in order to select the most appropriate machine learning algorithm(s) to solve the problem at hand.

As the first step, the focus is on the category of machine learning algorithm (Supervised Learning vs. Unsupervised Learning) that should be selected and the list of algorithms under each of these categories. Next, the fundamental questions that answer to them leads to narrow down the options to a smaller group and the final algorithm will be presented.

KEYWORDS:

Machine Learning Algorithms; Supervised Learning; Unsupervised Learning

BIOGRAPHY:

Marzieh Mehrjoo got her PhD in 2014 from the Engineering Faculty of University of Windsor, Canada. She has taught statistics to engineering and business student for more than three years. She is now the Data Science Team Lead at Dimensional Strategies Inc., a leading Microsoft technology consulting partner.